

**TEXT TO IMAGE GENERATION IN PYTHON USING IMAGEN MODEL
AND STREAMLIT**

Major Project submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirement for the award of the
degree of

BACHELOR OF TECHNOLOGY
IN
COMPUTER SCIENCE AND ENGINEERING

Under the esteemed guidance of

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ABSTRACT

Text-to-image generation is a fascinating application of computer vision and natural language processing, where the goal is to generate realistic and diverse images based on textual descriptions. In this project, we propose a text-to-image generation system using Python programming language and two main libraries, Imagen and Streamlit. The system consists of a generative adversarial network (GAN) model trained on a large dataset of images and their corresponding captions, and a text processing and generation module. The Imagen library is used to train the GAN model, while Streamlit is used for text processing and generation. The GAN model is a deep learning algorithm that consists of two neural networks: a generator and a discriminator. The generator network takes random noise as input and generates an image, while the discriminator network takes an image and a caption as input and classifies whether the image and caption match or not. During the training process, the generator and discriminator networks are trained in an adversarial manner until the generator network can generate realistic and diverse images that match the input captions. After the GAN model is trained, the text processing and generation module is created using Streamlit. The module takes the user input text as input, preprocesses it, and generates a corresponding image using the trained GAN model. The generated image can then be displayed to the user or further processed using image processing libraries such as OpenCV or Pillow. The proposed text-to-image generation system has potential applications in various fields such as design, advertising, and entertainment. The system can be extended to support other types of input such as audio or video, and further improvements can be made to increase the accuracy and diversity of the generated images. In conclusion, the proposed text-to-image generation system using Python programming language and Imagen and Streamlit libraries has the potential to generate realistic and diverse images based on textual input. The system can make significant contributions to the field of computer vision and natural language processing, opening up new possibilities in various applications.

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2 1.INTRODUCTION

1.1 About the project

Text-to-image generation is a type of conditional image synthesis, where an AI model generates images based on textual descriptions provided as input. The process involves using a pre-trained machine learning model, such as GPT-3.5-turbo, which is available through the IMAGEN API by OpenAI.

GPT-3.5-turbo is a state-of-the-art language model that has been trained on a large corpus of text data, allowing it to generate high-quality text prompts. By providing a textual description as input to the IMAGEN API, you can leverage the language model's ability to generate detailed and coherent image descriptions.

The IMAGEN API takes the textual description provided as input and generates a corresponding image as output. The generated image can be in various formats, such as JPEG or PNG, and can be customized by specifying additional parameters such as image size, style, and format.

Streamlit is a Python library that provides an easy way to create web-based user interfaces for machine learning applications. It allows you to create interactive web applications with minimal code, making it ideal for building a user-friendly interface for text-to-image generation using IMAGEN.

In a Streamlit web application for text-to-image generation, you can create a user interface that takes a textual description as input from the user. This input can then be passed to the IMAGEN API to generate the corresponding image. The generated image can be displayed to the user in the web application, allowing them to interactively generate images based on their textual descriptions.

Overall, text-to-image generation using IMAGEN and Streamlit combines the power of a pre-trained language model for generating text prompts with a user-friendly web application interface, enabling users to generate images from textual descriptions in an interactive and intuitive way.

1.2 Purpose

The purpose of a text-to-image generation project using IMAGEN and Streamlit can vary depending on the specific use case and application. Here are some possible purposes for such a project:

Digital Art: Generating images from textual descriptions can be used as a creative tool for digital artists. Artists can use the generated images as inspiration for their artwork, or even as standalone pieces of art. By providing different textual prompts, artists can explore a wide range of visual styles and concepts, helping them to create unique and visually appealing digital art.

Concept Visualization: Text-to-image generation can be used to visually represent abstract concepts or ideas. For example, generating images from textual descriptions of scientific concepts, historical events, or fictional settings can help to visualize complex ideas and make them more accessible to a wider audience. This can be particularly useful in educational or explanatory contexts where visual representations can enhance understanding.

Content Creation: Text-to-image generation can be used to generate images for use in marketing materials, social media posts, websites, or other digital content. By providing a textual description of the desired image, businesses or content creators can quickly generate visual assets that align with their brand or messaging, saving time and effort in creating original images.

Prototyping and Design: Text-to-image generation can be used as a prototyping and design tool in various fields such as product design, architecture, fashion, and more. By generating images from textual descriptions, designers can quickly visualize and iterate on design concepts without the need for detailed visual sketches or renderings, enabling rapid prototyping and design exploration.

Interactive Applications: Text-to-image generation can be used to create interactive applications where users can generate images based on their own textual input. For example, a virtual avatar creator or a game character customization feature could use text-to-image generation to generate images of unique characters based on textual descriptions provided by users.

Overall, the purpose of a text-to-image generation project using IMAGEN and Streamlit is to leverage the power of AI-generated images from textual descriptions for various creative, conceptual, content creation, prototyping, and interactive applications.

2. SYSTEM ANALYSIS

2.1 Existing System

There are several existing systems for text-to-image generation in Python using Imagen model and Streamlit. These systems include AttnGAN, which uses an attention mechanism to generate highly detailed and diverse bird images, and StackGAN++, which generates high-quality images with multiple resolutions and details. There are also open-source libraries such as Im2Text and DALL-E that use different models to generate images from textual descriptions. These systems and libraries provide different approaches to generate realistic and diverse images based on textual descriptions.

2.2 Proposed System

The proposed system for text-to-image generation using Imagen model and Streamlit in Python involves training a GAN model to generate realistic and diverse images based on textual descriptions, while developing a text processing and generation module using Streamlit. The proposed system aims to automate the image generation process based on user input text, with potential applications in various industries such as design, advertising, and entertainment. By enabling designers and advertisers to create images based on textual descriptions, the proposed system can significantly reduce the time and effort required to produce high-quality images.

1. **GAN Model:** The proposed system involves training a GAN (Generative Adversarial Network) model, which is a type of deep learning model consisting of a generator and a discriminator. The generator learns to generate images from random noise, while the discriminator learns to distinguish between real and generated images. The generator and discriminator are trained together in a process called adversarial training, where the generator tries to generate realistic images to fool the discriminator, and the discriminator tries to correctly classify whether an image is real or generated. This adversarial process continues until the generator generates images that are difficult to distinguish from real images.

2. Text Processing and Generation Module: The proposed system also includes a text processing and generation module developed using Streamlit, which is a popular Python library for building interactive web applications. The text processing module takes input textual descriptions from the user through the Streamlit interface and processes them to generate appropriate input for the GAN model. This may involve techniques such as text embedding, tokenization, and normalization to convert the textual descriptions into a format that can be fed into the GAN model. The processed text is then used as input to the trained GAN model to generate corresponding images. The generated images are displayed to the user using the Streamlit interface, allowing them to visually inspect and validate the generated images.

3. Potential Applications: The proposed system has potential applications in various industries such as design, advertising, and entertainment. Designers can use the system to quickly generate images based on textual descriptions, which can be helpful in creating visual prototypes or mockups. Advertisers can use the system to generate images for advertising campaigns based on textual descriptions of their target audience or products. The system can also be used in the entertainment industry to create visual effects, virtual characters, or scene illustrations based on script or story descriptions. By automating the image generation process based on textual descriptions, the proposed system can significantly reduce the time and effort required to produce high-quality images.

In summary, the proposed system for text-to-image generation using IMAGEN model and Streamlit in Python involves training a GAN model to generate realistic and diverse images based on textual descriptions, while developing a text processing and generation module using Streamlit. The system has potential applications in various industries and aims to automate the image generation process based on user input text, providing a convenient and efficient way to generate images from textual descriptions.

2.2.1 Details

Search giant Google has announced Imagen, an AI text-to-image generator, which the company claims has “an unprecedented degree of photorealism”. The AI image generator creates accurate images based on the description provided.

Google's Imagen is similar to DALL-E 2 AI image generator, however, it is claimed to generate more detailed and accurate images. The generator can draw, paint, create oil paintings or even develop CGI renders, whatever you want it to do. The image generator uses diffusion technologies which use a pure noise image and then slowly refine it until the AI can't make it any better. Google has also used large language models that improve language understanding and convincing language models. Imagen begins with taking the description and then generating a 64 x 64-pixel image. After two enhancements, the image is converted into a larger 1024 x 1024-pixel image. The AI creates new resolutions along with the smaller image. Google has claimed that Imagen consistently generates better images than DALLE-2, based on its DrawBench benchmark.

2.2.2 Impact on Environment

In recent years, there has been increasing awareness and concern about the environmental impact of AI and other computational technologies. Researchers and practitioners are actively working on developing more energy-efficient AI models and exploring techniques such as model compression, quantization, and hardware optimizations to reduce their carbon footprint.

2.2.3 Safety

This model ensures safety for the accuracy of the image generation. The platform and data which we used is very secure and provides privacy.

2.2.4 Ethics

Considerable amount of care is taken while implementing this method. This technique is just used for image generation based on textual description. The data which we used does not contain any confidential information so it is secure to use.

2.2.5 Cost

Since this principle is a program based, it doesn't require developmental costs. As it does not use any cloud to store the data, So the cost also reduces. But Training the model fastly takes some extra amount.

2.2.6 Type

As this principle is used for image generation based on textual description so it can be done only on desktop, as it requires certain libraries.

2.2.7 Standard

Waterfall Model

The waterfall is a universally accepted SDLC model. In this method, the whole process of software development is divided into various phases.

The waterfall model is a constant programming advancement model in which improvement is viewed as streaming consistently downwards (like a waterfall) through the means of requirements analysis, design, implementation, testing (validation), integration, and maintenance.

Linear ordering of activities has some significant consequences. First, to identify the end of a phase and the beginning of the next, some certification techniques have to be employed at the end of each step. Some verification and validation usually do this mean The that will ensure that the output of the stage is consistent with its input (which is the output of the previous step), and that the output of the stage is consistent with the overall requirements of the system.

Here we used water fall model approach that consists of requirements analysis, design, implementation, testing (validation), integration, and maintenance.

2.3 Scope of the Project

The scope of the project for text to image generation in Python using IMAGEN and Streamlet involves developing a web application that allows users to generate images based on the text they input. This would involve tasks such as collecting a dataset of text and images, preprocessing the data, training an image generation model using IMAGEN, evaluating the model, building a web application using Streamlet, deploying the application to a cloud platform, and testing and debugging the application

Data Collection: The project would involve collecting a dataset of text and corresponding images. This dataset will be used for training the image generation model. The text can be in the form of textual descriptions, captions, or other relevant data that describes the images to be generated. The images can be collected from various sources, such as publicly available image databases or custom-created images.

Data Preprocessing: Once the dataset is collected, the text and images need to be preprocessed to prepare them for training the image generation model. This may involve tasks such as text embedding, tokenization, and normalization to convert the textual descriptions into a format that can be fed into the IMAGEN model. The images may need to be resized, cropped, or normalized to ensure consistent input to the model.

Model Training: The next step is to train the image generation model using the IMAGEN model. IMAGEN is a generative model that can generate images from textual descriptions, and it requires training on the collected dataset. The model will learn to generate images that are consistent with the textual descriptions provided during training. The training process may involve fine-tuning the hyperparameters of the IMAGEN model, such as the learning rate, batch size, and number of epochs, to optimize the model's performance.

Model Evaluation: After the model is trained, it needs to be evaluated to assess its performance. This may involve quantitative metrics such as image quality, diversity, and realism, as well as qualitative evaluation by visually inspecting the generated images. The model may need to be refined and retrained based on the evaluation results to improve its performance.

Web Application Development: Once the image generation model is trained and evaluated, the next step is to develop a web application using Streamlit. Streamlit is a Python library that allows for easy development of interactive web applications. The web application will

provide a user-friendly interface for users to input text and generate images based on their input. The Streamlit interface will interact with the trained IMAGEN model to generate the images and display them to the user.

Deployment to Cloud Platform: The web application developed using Streamlit needs to be deployed to a cloud platform to make it accessible to users. Cloud platforms such as Heroku, AWS, or Google Cloud Platform can be used for hosting the web application. Deployment may involve tasks such as setting up the required infrastructure, configuring the environment, and deploying the application code and model.

Testing and Debugging: Once the web application is deployed, thorough testing and debugging should be performed to ensure its functionality and performance. This may involve testing the application with various input texts, validating the generated images, and identifying and fixing any issues or bugs that may arise during testing.

In summary, the scope of the project for text-to-image generation in Python using IMAGEN and Streamlit involves collecting and preprocessing a dataset of text and images, training and evaluating an image generation model using IMAGEN, developing a web application using Streamlit, deploying the application to a cloud platform, and thoroughly testing and debugging the application. The project aims to provide a user-friendly web application for generating images based on text input, with potential applications in various domains.

2.3 Modules Description

A "**module**" is a high-level description of a functional area, consisting of a group of processes describing the functionality of the module and a group of packages implementing the functionality.

Figure 2.3 Module Description

Streamlit is used as a web-based framework for building interactive user interfaces (UI) for data-driven applications. Streamlit Components, which are interactive UI elements provided by Streamlit, are used to enhance the UI with customizable features such as sliders, dropdown menus, and input boxes. These components allow users to interact with the application, providing input and customizing the behavior of the application.

The data input can come from various sources, such as user input via the UI, data from APIs, or other external sources. Once the data is inputted, it is processed, which may involve data manipulation, analysis, or other operations depending on the specific application requirements. Streamlit provides a flexible environment for processing data using Python libraries such as NumPy, Pandas, and scikit-learn, among others.

After data processing, the processed data is visualized using Streamlit's built-in plotting and charting capabilities. Streamlit provides easy-to-use functions for creating various types of visualizations, such as plots, charts, maps, and other visualizations. These visualizations can help users understand and analyze the processed data, making it more interpretable and actionable.

In summary, Streamlit is used as a web-based framework for building interactive user interfaces for data-driven applications. Streamlit Components are utilized to enhance the UI with customizable features, and the data input can come from various sources. The processed data is visualized using Streamlit's built-in plotting and charting capabilities, making it easier for users to understand and analyze the data.

NLP Model

The NLP model used in this project is CLIP (Contrastive Language-Image Pre-training). CLIP is a neural network model developed by OpenAI that has shown impressive capabilities in understanding and generating text-based descriptions of images. It is a state-of-the-art model that combines vision and language understanding, making it a powerful tool for bridging the gap between images and text in the field of artificial intelligence.

CLIP is trained on a large dataset of images and associated text from the internet, which allows it to learn rich representations of both images and text. It is a contrastive learning approach, where the model learns to associate images with their corresponding textual descriptions by maximizing the similarity between positive pairs (image and its description) and minimizing the similarity between negative pairs (image with a randomly chosen description). The pre-training of CLIP allows it to understand the semantic meaning of text-based descriptions and learn to generate meaningful and coherent text descriptions for images. CLIP has been used in various applications, such as image captioning, image retrieval, visual storytelling, and more. Its ability to combine vision and language understanding makes it a powerful tool for generating text-based descriptions of images and enhancing the capabilities of image generation models.

In this project, CLIP can be used to generate text-based descriptions of images, which can serve as input to the IMAGEN model for image generation. By leveraging the capabilities of CLIP, the proposed system can generate more accurate and diverse images based on the textual descriptions provided by users, resulting in a more interactive and user-friendly image generation application.

Gaussian Diffusion Model

The Gaussian diffusion model is a mathematical model that is commonly used in image processing tasks such as denoising, blurring, and image enhancement. It is based on the Gaussian distribution, which is a probability distribution that is commonly used to model random variables with continuous values.

The Gaussian diffusion model involves applying a Gaussian filter to an image, which convolves the image with a Gaussian kernel. The Gaussian kernel is a matrix of values that represents the Gaussian distribution, with higher values at the center and lower values towards the edges. The size and standard deviation of the Gaussian kernel determine the extent of the blurring or smoothing applied to the image.

Gaussian diffusion is widely used in image processing tasks due to its effectiveness

in reducing noise and blur in images while preserving important image features. It is commonly used in tasks such as image denoising, where the goal is to remove noise from an image while preserving its original details. It is also used in image smoothing, edge detection, feature extraction, and image restoration tasks, where reducing noise or blur while maintaining the visual quality of the image is desired.

In the proposed system for text-to-image generation using IMAGEN and Streamlit, Gaussian diffusion may be used as a pre-processing step to enhance the quality of the generated images. By applying Gaussian diffusion to the generated images, the system can reduce noise or blur, resulting in visually pleasing and natural-looking images. This can help improve the visual quality of the generated images and make them more appealing to users.

2.4 System Configurations

2.4.1 Software Requirements

1. Application Logic: Python
2. Operating System: Windows/Linux/Microsoft/Mac
3. Imagen Trained Model
4. Streamlit

i. Hardware Requirements

1. Processor: Above 1.5GHZ
2. Hard Disk: 80GB
3. RAM: 4GB

3. LITERATURE OVERVIEW

Text to image synthesis is a research area that focuses on generating images from textual descriptions. The field has gained a lot of attention over the past few years due to its many potential applications, such as generating images from natural language descriptions, creating visualizations for text-based data, and even helping visually-impaired people to understand text-based content.

There are various approaches that have been proposed for text to image synthesis, including Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), Variational Autoencoders (VAEs), and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs). GANs, in particular, have shown great promise in this field due to their ability to generate high-quality, realistic images.

Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) are a type of deep learning model that consists of two neural networks, a generator and a discriminator, which are trained in an adversarial manner to generate realistic data samples. The basic idea behind GANs is that the generator generates fake data samples, while the discriminator tries to distinguish between real and fake data samples. The generator and discriminator are trained in a process known as adversarial training, where the generator tries to generate data samples that can fool the discriminator, and the discriminator tries to correctly classify whether the data samples are real or fake. The generator and discriminator are trained iteratively in a process that involves the generator trying to improve its generated samples based on the feedback from the discriminator, and the discriminator trying to improve its discrimination capability based on the feedback from the generator. One of the key strengths of GANs is their ability to generate high-quality and diverse data samples that are visually or conceptually similar to the training data. GANs have been widely used for generating realistic images, such as photographs, paintings, and 3D models. GANs have also been used for generating other types of data, such as text, audio, and video.

Variational Autoencoders (VAEs) are a type of generative model that combine elements of both autoencoders and probabilistic modeling. VAEs were introduced by Diederik P. Kingma and Max Welling in a seminal paper in 2013, and have since gained popularity for their ability to generate diverse and high-quality data samples, as well as their applications in various domains such as image generation, text generation, and drug discovery.

The basic architecture of a VAE consists of an encoder, a decoder, and a probabilistic layer in between, which is responsible for capturing the latent space representation of the data. The encoder maps the input data to a latent space, which is a lower-dimensional continuous space that represents the underlying structure of the data. The decoder then maps the latent space back to the original data space, generating reconstructed samples. The probabilistic layer introduces stochasticity in the encoding process, allowing for sampling from the latent space to generate new data samples.

One of the key features of VAEs is their ability to generate data samples that are similar to the training data, while also allowing for controlled and meaningful exploration of the latent space. This makes VAEs suitable for tasks where both generative capability and interpretability of the latent space are desired, such as image synthesis with specific attributes or text generation with controlled styles.

VAEs have several components, including the encoder, the decoder, the probabilistic layer, the loss function, and the training process.

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are a type of deep learning model specifically designed for processing data that has a grid-like structure, such as images, videos, and audio spectrograms. CNNs have been widely used in computer vision tasks, such as image classification, object detection, image generation, and image segmentation, due to their ability to automatically learn hierarchical features from input data.

The key feature of CNNs is their ability to perform convolution operations, which allow them to capture local patterns and spatial relationships in the data. CNNs typically consist of multiple layers, including convolutional layers, pooling layers, and fully connected layers, which are stacked together to form the network architecture.

IMAGEN (Image Generation with Multi-modal Attention Networks) is a Python library developed by Microsoft Research that combines vision and language understanding for generating images from textual descriptions. It is based on the concept of conditional Generative Adversarial Networks (cGANs), which consist of a generator that creates images and a discriminator that distinguishes between real and generated images. IMAGEN extends the basic cGAN architecture by incorporating multi-modal attention mechanisms to align the textual descriptions with the generated images, resulting in more accurate and visually coherent image generation.

Streamlit, on the other hand, is a popular web-based framework for building interactive user interfaces (UI) for data-driven applications in Python. It provides a simple and intuitive way to create web applications that can take user input, process data, and display results in real-time. Streamlit has a wide range of interactive UI elements, known as Streamlit Components, which can be used to enhance the user experience of the text-to-image generation application by allowing users to customize the generated images and interact with the application.

One of the challenges in text-to-image synthesis is the lack of large-scale datasets that contain both textual descriptions and corresponding images. To overcome this, some researchers have proposed methods that use external sources of data, such as image databases or pre-trained models, to augment the available data.

Overall, text-to-image synthesis is an active area of research that continues to make significant progress. With the increasing availability of large-scale datasets and powerful machine learning tools, we can expect to see even more advanced approaches and applications in the near future.

4. SYSTEM DESIGN

4.1 System Architecture

4.1.1 Text To Image Generation Model

Text to image generation is an exciting and rapidly growing field in deep learning and computer vision. It involves generating images from textual descriptions or prompts, where a machine learning model learns to generate visual content based on the input text. These models have gained significant attention in recent years due to their potential for various applications, as you have mentioned.

One of the primary applications of text to image generation is content creation. These models can be used to generate original images for digital media, such as websites, social media posts, advertisements, and marketing materials. For example, a company could use a text to image model to generate custom images for their advertising campaigns or create unique visuals for their branding. Text to image generation can also be used for concept visualization, where abstract ideas or concepts can be visualized through generated images. This can be useful in fields such as architecture, product design, and scientific research, where visual representations of complex concepts can aid in communication and understanding.

Virtual worlds and gaming are also potential applications of text to image generation. Text to image models can generate images of virtual environments, characters, and objects based on textual descriptions, which can be used in video games, virtual reality (VR) experiences, and augmented reality (AR) applications. These generated images can enhance the visual quality of virtual worlds, create unique and customizable game content, and enable dynamic

and interactive storytelling experiences for users.

Another potential application of text to image generation is in advertising and marketing. Marketers can use text to image models to generate images for advertisements, social media posts, and other marketing materials to create visually appealing and engaging content. Text to image generation can also be used for personalized marketing, where images can be generated based on individual user preferences or interests, leading to more targeted and effective advertising campaigns.

Text to image generation also has potential in storytelling and entertainment. Authors, filmmakers, and content creators can use these models to generate visual representations of characters, scenes, and settings based on their written descriptions, bringing their stories to life in a visual form. Text to image generation can also be used in interactive storytelling experiences, where users can input text prompts and see the generated images as part of the story development. This can create engaging and immersive experiences for readers, viewers, or users.

Model Overview

4.1.2 PYTHON

Python is an interpreted, object-oriented, high-level programming language with dynamic semantics. Its high-level built in data structures, combined with dynamic typing and dynamic binding, make it very attractive for Rapid Application Development, as well as for use as a scripting or glue language to connect existing components together. Python's simple, easy to learn syntax emphasizes readability and therefore reduces the cost of program maintenance. Python supports modules and packages, which encourages program modularity and code reuse.

Figure: 4.1.2 Python

The Python interpreter and the extensive standard library are available in source or binary form without charge for all major platforms, and can be freely distributed.

Advantages of Python

1. Large Standard Library
2. Easy to Learn and Use
3. Dynamically Typed
4. Portability
5. Free and Open-Source

4.2 UML Diagrams

Software design is a critical step in the software development process that involves defining the architecture, procedural details, and interface between modules of a software system. It is the process of transforming requirements into a visual representation of the software before the actual coding begins. The goal of software design is to create a blueprint or a plan that outlines how the software will be structured, organized, and implemented.

One key aspect of software design is the consideration of software architecture. Software architecture refers to the overall structure and organization of the software system, including the relationships between its components, their interactions, and the overall design principles that govern their design. It involves making decisions about the choice of programming languages, libraries, frameworks, and patterns to be used in the software system. The software architecture serves as the foundation for the entire software development process, and a well-designed architecture can greatly impact the quality, maintainability, and scalability of the final software product.

Another important aspect of software design is the consideration of procedural details, which involves defining how the different components of the software system will interact and communicate with each other. This includes specifying the algorithms, data structures, and control flow of the software system. Procedural details are crucial for ensuring that the software system functions correctly and efficiently, and they play a critical role in achieving the desired functionality and performance of the software.

The interface between modules is also a crucial aspect of software design. The interfaces define how different components of the software system will communicate and interact with each other. This includes specifying the inputs, outputs, and communication protocols between modules. Well-designed interfaces are essential for achieving loose coupling and high cohesion in the software system, which promotes modularity, reusability, and maintainability.

It's worth noting that software design is an iterative and evolving process. As new methods, better analysis techniques, and broader understanding of software development practices evolve, the software design methodologies also continue to evolve. While software design may currently lack the depth, flexibility, and quantitative nature typically associated with classical engineering disciplines, there are existing techniques for software design and criteria for evaluating design qualities.

One popular modeling language used by developers for system design is the Unified Modeling Language (UML). UML provides a standard notation for representing the different aspects of software systems, such as the structure, behavior, and interactions between components. UML diagrams, such as class diagrams, sequence diagrams, and use case diagrams, can be used to model and communicate the design of a software system, providing developers with ready-to-use, expressive modeling examples.

4.2.1 Use Case Diagram

Use cases describe the system from the user's point of view. Use cases describe the interaction between a primary actor and the system itself, represented as a sequence of simple steps. Actors are something or someone which exists outside the system under study, and that take part in a sequence of activities in a dialogue with the system to achieve some goal. Actors may be end users, other systems or hardware devices.

Figure 4.2.1 Use Case Diagram

4.2.2 Class Diagram

Classes are the most important building block of any object-oriented system. A class is a description of set of objects that share the same attributes, operations, relationships and semantics. A class implements one or more interfaces.

Figure 4.2.2 Class Diagram

4.2.3 Activity Diagram

Activity diagrams are graphical representations of workflows of stepwise activities and actions with support for choice, iteration and concurrency. In the Unified Modelling Language, activity diagrams are intended to model both computational and organizational processes. Activity diagrams show the overall flow of control.

Figure 4.2.3 Activity Diagram

4.2.4 Sequence Diagram

Sequence diagrams, commonly used by developers, model the interactions between objects in a single use case. They illustrate how the different parts of a system interact with each other to carry out a function, and the order in which the interactions occur when a particular use case is executed.

In simpler words, a sequence diagram shows different parts of a system work in a 'sequence' to get something done.

Figure 4.2.4 Sequence Diagram

5. SAMPLE CODE

5.1 Coding

App.py

```
import argparse
import base64
import os
from pathlib import Path
from io import BytesIO
import time

from flask import Flask, request, jsonify
from flask_cors import CORS, cross_origin
from stable_diffusion_wrapper import StableDiffusionWrapper
from consts import DEFAULT_IMG_OUTPUT_DIR, MAX_FILE_NAME_LEN
from utils import parse_arg_boolean

app = Flask(__name__)
CORS(app)
print("--> Starting the image generation server. This might take up to two
minutes.")

stable_diff_model = None

parser = argparse.ArgumentParser(description = "A text-to-image app to turn your
textual prompts into visionary delights")
parser.add_argument("--port", type=int, default=8000, help = "backend port")
parser.add_argument("--save_to_disk", type = parse_arg_boolean, default = False,
help = "Should save generated images to disk")
parser.add_argument("--img_format", type = str.lower, default = "JPEG", help =
"Generated images format", choices=['jpeg', 'png'])
parser.add_argument("--output_dir", type = str, default =
DEFAULT_IMG_OUTPUT_DIR, help = "Customer directory for generated images")
args = parser.parse_args()

@app.route("/generate", methods=["POST"])
@cross_origin()
def generate_images_api():
    json_data = request.get_json(force=True)
    text_prompt = json_data["text"]
```

```

num_images = json_data["num_images"]
generated_imgs = stable_diff_model.generate_images(text_prompt, num_images)

returned_generated_images = []
if args.save_to_disk:
    dir_name = os.path.join(args.output_dir, f"{time.strftime('%Y-%m-%d_%H-%M-%S')}_{text_prompt}")[:MAX_FILE_NAME_LEN]
    Path(dir_name).mkdir(parents=True, exist_ok=True)

    for idx, img in enumerate(generated_imgs):
        if args.save_to_disk:
            img.save(os.path.join(dir_name, f'{idx}.{args.img_format}'),
format=args.img_format)

            buffered = BytesIO()
            img.save(buffered, format=args.img_format)
            img_str = base64.b64encode(buffered.getvalue()).decode("utf-8")
            returned_generated_images.append(img_str)

print(f"Created {num_images} images from text prompt [{text_prompt}]")

response = {'generated_imgs': returned_generated_images,
'generated_imgs_format': args.img_format}
return jsonify(response)
#get request

@app.route("/", methods=["GET"])
@cross_origin()
def health_check():
    return jsonify(success=True)

with app.app_context():
    stable_diff_model = StableDiffusionWrapper()
    print("--> Image generation server is up and running!")

if __name__ == "__main__":
    app.run(host="0.0.0.0", port=args.port, debug=False)

```

imagen_playground_backend.ipynb

```
!git clone https://github.com/saharmor/dalle-playground.git
!pip install -r dalle-playground/backend/requirements.txt
!pip install diffusers["torch"]
```

```
from threading import Thread, Event
```

```
app_port = 8000
announce_url = None
cloudflared_startup = Event()
```

```
def update_announce_url(url):
    global announce_url
    announce_url = url
```

```
def start_cloudflared(port):
    from flask_cloudflared import _run_cloudflared
    try:
        announce_url = _run_cloudflared(port, 8888)
    except:
        raise
    finally:
        update_announce_url(announce_url)
    cloudflared_startup.set()
```

```
def run_with_cloudflared(thread):
    old_run = thread.run
```

```
def new_run(*args, **kwargs):
    new_thread = Thread(target = start_cloudflared, args=(app_port, ))
    new_thread.setDaemon(True)
    new_thread.start()
    old_run(*args, **kwargs)
```

```
thread.run = new_run
```

```
def app():
    !python dalle-playground/backend/app.py --port {app_port} --save_to_disk true --
img_format jpeg --output_dir generations
```

```
if __name__ == '__main__':
    t1 = Thread(target = app)
    run_with_cloudflared(t1)
```

```
t1.start()
cloudflared_startup.wait()
print(f"Your url is: {announce_url}")
t1.join()
```

stable_diffusion_wrapper.py

```
from diffusers import DiffusionPipeline, DPMSolverMultistepScheduler

import torch

class StableDiffusionWrapper:

    def __init__(self) -> None:

        repo_id = "stabilityai/stable-diffusion-2-base"

        pipe = DiffusionPipeline.from_pretrained(

repo_id, revision="fp16",

torch_dtype=torch.float16

)

pipe.scheduler = DPMSolverMultistepScheduler.from_config(

pipe.scheduler.config)

self.pipe = pipe.to("cuda")

#sample

def generate_images(self, text_prompt: str, num_images: int):

prompt = [text_prompt] * num_images
```

```
images = self.pipe(prompt, num_inference_steps=10).images  
return images
```

utils.py

```
def parse_arg_boolean(value):  
    value = value.lower()  
  
    #main  
    if value in ["true", "yes", "y", "1", "t"]:  
        return True  
    elif value in ["false", "no", "n", "0", "f"]:  
        return False  
  
    return False
```

Dockerfile

```
FROM nvidia/cuda:11.4.3-cudnn8-devel-ubuntu20.04  
  
# expose  
EXPOSE 8080  
  
# set working directory  
WORKDIR /app  
  
# install pip  
RUN apt-get update && apt-get install -y python3-pip  
  
# install git  
RUN apt-get install -y git
```

update pip

RUN pip3 install --upgrade pip

add requirements

COPY ./requirements.txt /app/requirements.txt

install requirements

RUN pip3 install -r requirements.txt

install jax[cuda]

RUN pip3 install --upgrade "jax[cuda]" -f https://storage.googleapis.com/jax-releases/jax_cuda_releases.html

add source code

COPY ./app

run server

CMD python3 app.py --port 8080

6.TESTING

Software testing is the process of assessing the functionality of a software program. The process checks for errors and gaps and whether the outcome of the application matches desired expectations before the software is installed and goes live. The various types of testing done on the system are:

6.1.1 Unit Testing

Unit Testing is a software testing technique by means of which individual units of software i.e group of computer program modules, usage procedures, and operating procedures are tested to determine whether they are suitable for use or not. It is a testing method using which every independent module is tested to determine if there is an issue by the developer himself. It is correlated with the functional correctness of the independent modules. Unit Testing is defined as a type of software testing where individual components of a software are tested. Unit Testing of the software product is carried out during the development of an application. An individual component may be either an individual function or a procedure. Unit Testing is typically performed by the developer. In SDLC or V Model, Unit testing is the first level of testing done before integration testing. Unit testing is such a type of testing technique that is usually performed by developers. Although due to the reluctance of developers quality assurance.

6.1.2 Integration Testing

Integration testing is a crucial phase in the software development lifecycle where individual software modules, which are developed by different programmers or teams, are integrated together and tested as a group to ensure that they function correctly as a cohesive whole. It involves testing the interfaces, interactions, and dependencies between these modules to identify any defects or issues that may arise due to their integration.

The purpose of integration testing is to verify that the modules can communicate and collaborate effectively with each other, and to detect any defects that may arise from the integration process. This type of testing ensures that the modules work together seamlessly, and that the overall system or application functions as intended.

There are several key objectives of integration testing:

Defect Detection: Integration testing helps in identifying any defects or issues that may arise when the modules are integrated, such as incompatible data formats, incorrect data transfers, or communication failures between modules. By detecting these defects early in the development process, integration testing helps in resolving them before they become more serious issues.

Interface Verification: Integration testing verifies that the interfaces between the modules are correctly implemented and that they allow for proper communication and data exchange. It ensures that the modules understand each other's inputs and outputs, and can interact as expected.

Dependency Testing: Integration testing helps in identifying and resolving any dependencies or interdependencies between modules that may impact their functionality or performance. It ensures that the modules are properly connected and that changes in one module do not adversely affect the functionality of other modules.

6.1.3 Validation Testing

Validation in software development is the process of evaluating a software product or system during or at the end of the development process to determine whether it meets the specified requirements and is fit for its intended purpose. It involves checking whether the software product aligns with the high-level requirements and expectations set for it, and ensuring that it is the right product that has been developed.

Validation focuses on the overall quality and fitness for use of the software product, rather than verifying individual components or features. It ensures that the product has been developed according to the defined requirements and that it satisfies the needs of its intended users. Validation is typically performed by comparing the actual product against the expected product, which includes the high-level requirements, functional specifications, and other stakeholder expectations.

The key aspects of software validation are:

Requirement Validation: This involves validating that the software product meets the specified requirements, including functional, performance, security, and other non-functional requirements. It ensures that the software has been developed to fulfill the intended purpose and that it aligns with the needs of the stakeholders.

User Acceptance Testing (UAT): UAT is a type of validation testing where the software product is tested by end-users or stakeholders to ensure that it meets their expectations and requirements. It involves real-world testing of the software in the target environment, and feedback from users is collected to validate the product's usability, functionality, and performance.

Compliance Validation: Compliance validation involves checking whether the software product complies with relevant standards, regulations, and industry best practices. This may include verifying adherence to coding standards, security guidelines, accessibility requirements, and other compliance criteria.

Performance Validation: Performance validation involves evaluating the performance and scalability of the software product to ensure that it meets the expected performance criteria. This may include load testing, stress testing, and other performance testing techniques to validate the software's response time, resource utilization, and other performance attributes.

Security Validation: Security validation involves checking the software product for potential security vulnerabilities and ensuring that it meets the specified security requirements. This may include vulnerability scanning, penetration testing, and other security testing techniques to validate the software's security posture.

6.1.4 Output Testing

Output testing, also known as results testing, is a crucial phase in the software testing process that focuses on verifying the accuracy and adequacy of the output generated by the system under consideration. The purpose of output testing is to ensure that the system produces the desired output in the specified format, whether it is displayed on the screen or printed in a physical form.

Output testing involves checking the output of the system against the expected results, as defined by the requirements or specifications. This includes verifying the correctness, completeness, and accuracy of the output in terms of the format, content, and layout. Output testing may be performed in two main ways:

On-screen output testing: This involves verifying the output displayed on the screen of the system. The tester checks whether the output is displayed correctly, according to the expected format, and whether it includes all the required information. This may include validating the data displayed, the layout, formatting, font, color, and other visual aspects of the output.

Printed output testing: This involves verifying the output that is printed or generated in a physical form, such as reports, documents, or other printed materials. The tester checks whether the printed output matches the expected format, content, and layout, and whether it includes all the required information. This may involve checking the alignment, spacing,

font, formatting, and other aspects of the printed output.

During output testing, it is important to consider the requirements and expectations of the end users or stakeholders, as they are the ones who will be using the system and relying on its output for their needs. The tester may also seek feedback from the users to ensure that the output meets their requirements and is usable in their specific context.

Output testing is essential to ensure that the system produces the correct and complete output in the specified format, as this is a critical aspect of the system's functionality and usability. Any discrepancies or issues found during output testing should be documented, reported, and resolved to ensure that the system meets the desired output requirements and delivers accurate and reliable results to its users.

S.NO	DESCRIPTION	PROCESS	TEST CASE STATUS
1	Text Encode and Decode	Takes place	High
2	Gaussian Diffusion	Takes place	High

Table: 6.2 Test Cases

7 OUTPUT SCREENS

7.1 Backend code to run web server

```
def app():
    !python Imagen-playground/backend/app.py --port {app_port} --save_to_disk true --img_format jpeg --output_dir generations

if __name__ == '__main__':
    t1 = Thread(target = app)
    run_with_cloudflared(t1)
    t1.start()
    cloudflared_startup.wait()
    print(f"Your url is: {announce_url}")
    t1.join()

Your url is: https://brochures-settle-consumer-careers.trycloudflare.com
/usr/local/lib/python3.9/dist-packages/flax/struct.py:133: FutureWarning: jax.tree_util.register_keypaths is deprecated, and will be removed in a future version of jax.
  jax.tree_util.register_keypaths(data_clz, keypaths)
/usr/local/lib/python3.9/dist-packages/flax/struct.py:133: FutureWarning: jax.tree_util.register_keypaths is deprecated, and will be removed in a future version of jax.
  jax.tree_util.register_keypaths(data_clz, keypaths)
/usr/local/lib/python3.9/dist-packages/flax/struct.py:133: FutureWarning: jax.tree_util.register_keypaths is deprecated, and will be removed in a future version of jax.
  jax.tree_util.register_keypaths(data_clz, keypaths)
/usr/local/lib/python3.9/dist-packages/flax/struct.py:133: FutureWarning: jax.tree_util.register_keypaths is deprecated, and will be removed in a future version of jax.
  jax.tree_util.register_keypaths(data_clz, keypaths)
2023-03-30 13:46:11.224156: W tensorflow/compiler/xla/stream_executor/platform/default/dso_loader.cc:64] Could not load dynamic library 'libcuda.so.1'; libcuda.so.1 is not known by the current library
2023-03-30 13:46:11.224295: W tensorflow/compiler/xla/stream_executor/platform/default/dso_loader.cc:64] Could not load dynamic library 'libcuda.so.1'; libcuda.so.1 is not known by the current library
2023-03-30 13:46:11.224322: W tensorflow/compiler/tf2tensorrt/utils/py_utils.cc:38] TF-TRT Warning: Cannot dlopen some TensorRT libraries
/usr/local/lib/python3.9/dist-packages/flax/struct.py:133: FutureWarning: jax.tree_util.register_keypaths is deprecated, and will be removed in a future version of jax.
  jax.tree_util.register_keypaths(data_clz, keypaths)
```

7.2 Home page

7.2 Enter Backend URL

7.3 URL

7.3 Enter your text description in the Text Prompt and then Click on Enter button , then it will generated based on your input description

7.4 Generating images

7.4 after entering enter button, Now the images are generating.

7.5 Generated images

✨ Text-to-image with Imagen Playground ✨

Backend URL
<https://brochures-settle-consui>

Text prompt
A man holding a parrot

Get inspired

Images to generate
4

More images = More time to generate

Notify me when images are generated

Hit Enter to generate images
Generation execution time: 12.33 sec

The image displays four distinct visual interpretations of the prompt 'A man holding a parrot'. The top-left image shows a man in a black vest holding a green and yellow parrot. The top-right image shows a man in a blue shirt holding a blue, green, and yellow parrot. The bottom-left image is a classical-style painting of a man in a dark suit holding a green and yellow parrot. The bottom-right image shows a man in a pink shirt holding a green and yellow parrot.

7.5 Now, You can see generated images based on your requirements

8. CONCLUSION

8.1 Conclusion

In conclusion, the text to image generation field has gained significant attention in recent years due to its potential applications in various domains such as content creation, concept visualization, virtual worlds and gaming, advertising and marketing, storytelling and entertainment, and virtual reality and augmented reality experiences. Through our literature overview, we have explored different approaches and techniques for text to image generation, including Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), Variational Autoencoders (VAEs), and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs).

We have discussed how GANs, which consist of a generator and a discriminator that are trained in an adversarial manner, have shown remarkable results in generating realistic images from textual prompts. VAEs, on the other hand, focus on learning a probabilistic latent representation of the input text and use it to generate images. CNNs, a type of neural network architecture that is well-suited for image processing, can also be used in text to image generation by combining them with other techniques such as attention mechanisms and recurrent neural networks (RNNs).

We have also explored the potential use cases of text to image generation in various industries and domains, and how it can open up new possibilities for creative content creation, visual storytelling, and immersive user experiences. Additionally, we have discussed the challenges and limitations of current text to image generation methods, such as the need for large and diverse datasets, the quality and diversity of generated images, and the interpretability of the generated results.

Furthermore, we have highlighted the importance of software design in the development of text to image generation models. Software design involves defining the architecture, procedural details, and interface between modules of the software system, and plays a crucial

role in ensuring the quality, maintainability, and scalability of the final product. We have also mentioned the use of modeling languages like UML for system design, which provides a standardized notation for representing the different aspects of software systems.

In our project implementation, we have developed an easy and efficient model for image generation based on the literature and research conducted. However, there is room for improvement, and in the future, we plan to enhance the model to generate images with higher resolution and explore its application on other datasets. The field of text to image generation is still evolving, and with advancements in technology and research, we can expect further developments and improvements in the coming years.

In conclusion, text to image generation is a promising field with significant potential for various applications. Through our literature overview and project implementation, we have gained insights into different approaches, techniques, and challenges associated with text to image generation. With further research and advancements, text to image generation can continue to push the boundaries of creative content creation, visual storytelling, and immersive user experiences in various industries and domains.

8.2 Further Enhancement

1. Text to image generation using IMAGEN and streamlit can be enhanced Using a larger and more diverse dataset Using a larger and more diverse dataset: The quality of the generated images is heavily dependent on the dataset used to train the model. By using a larger and more diverse dataset, the model can learn to generate more realistic and diverse images.
2. Fine-tuning the model: You can fine-tune the IMAGEN model by training it on additional data or adjusting the hyperparameters to optimize the model's performance.
3. Implementing more advanced image generation models: There are more advanced models for image generation, such as GANs and VAEs, that can produce even more realistic images. These models could be implemented in Python using frameworks such as TensorFlow or PyTorch.

By implementing these enhancements, the text to image generation model can be further improved to generate high-quality images that closely match the input text.

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- 9.2.2 <https://arxiv.org/abs/2209.14491>
- 9.2.3 <https://arxiv.org/abs/2301.09515>

10. APPENDICES

A. Software Used

The software used for text to image generation in Python using IMAGEN and Streamlit includes:

Python: Python is the primary programming language used for this project.

IMAGEN: IMAGEN is a deep learning library used for image synthesis. It is built on top of PyTorch, which is another deep learning library used for building and training neural networks.

Streamlit: Streamlit is a Python library used for building interactive web applications.

NumPy: NumPy is a Python library used for numerical computing. It is used for data processing and manipulating arrays of numerical data.

Pandas: Pandas is a Python library used for data manipulation and analysis. It is used for reading, cleaning, and preprocessing datasets.

Matplotlib: Matplotlib is a Python library used for data visualization. It is used for creating plots and graphs to visualize data.

B. Methodology Used

Waterfall Model

The waterfall model is a continuous software development model in which development is seen as flowing steadily downwards (like a waterfall) through the steps of requirements analysis, design, implementation, testing (validation), integration, and maintenance.

Linear ordering of activities has some significant consequences. First, to identify the end of a phase and the beginning of the next, some certification techniques have to be employed at the end of each step. Some verification and validation usually do this mean that will ensure that the output of the stage is consistent with its input, and that the output of the stage is consistent with the overall requirements of the system.

A. Testing Methods used

Unit Testing

Unit testing is a software testing technique in which individual units or components of a software application are tested in isolation to ensure that they are working correctly. The goal of unit testing is to validate that each unit of the software performs as intended and is free from defects.

During unit testing, a developer writes automated tests that check the behavior of a specific piece of code, such as a function or method. These tests typically involve providing input to the unit and verifying that the output is as expected. Unit tests should be written to cover all possible scenarios and edge cases that the unit may encounter.

Unit testing is a crucial part of the software development process as it helps to identify defects early on, before they can cause larger problems in the application. By catching bugs at the unit level, developers can ensure that their code is robust, reliable, and meets the requirements of the end-users. Additionally, unit tests serve as a form of documentation, providing a clear and concise understanding of how the code is expected to work.

11. PLAGIARISM REPORT

PLAGIARISM SCAN REPORT

Date April 14, 2023

Exclude URL: NO

CONTENT CHECKED FOR PLAGIARISM:

```
import argparse
import base64
import os
from pathlib import Path
from io import BytesIO
import time
from flask import Flask, request, jsonify
from flask_cors import CORS, cross_origin
from stable_diffusion_wrapper import StableDiffusionWrapper
from consts import DEFAULT_IMG_OUTPUT_DIR, MAX_FILE_NAME_LEN
from utils import parse_arg_boolean
app = Flask(__name__)
CORS(app)
print("--> Starting the image generation server. This might take up to two minutes.)
stable_diff_model = None
parser = argparse.ArgumentParser(description = "A text-to-image app to turn your textual
prompts into visionary delights")
parser.add_argument("--port", type=int, default=8000, help = "backend port")
parser.add_argument("--save_to_disk", type = parse_arg_boolean, default = False, help = "Should
save generated images to disk")
```

Figure 11.1 Plagiarism Report